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Wild Animal Species Threatened By Poachers and Perception of Respondents toward Poaching in Gujba Forest Reserve, Yobe State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assesses poaching activities within the Gujba Forest Reserve. The research aims to identify wild animal species threatened by poaching and to evaluate respondents' perceptions of poaching in the reserve. Primary data were collected through 200 structured questionnaires, randomly administered to hunters, bushmeat sellers, forest guards, firewood sellers, civil servants, and residents of seven communities surrounding the forest reserve. Secondary data were obtained from relevant literature and journals. Data analysis employed descriptive statistical techniques, and the chi-square test was conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22. Results indicate that the calculated chi-square value exceeded the critical tabulated value at $\alpha = 0.05\%$. Findings reveal that 75% of respondents had Arabic education, and 35% belonged to the age group of 31-40 years. Poachers earn between N6,000 and N10,000 per week, and 85% of respondents were aware of the destruction caused by poachers within the Gujba Forest Reserve. Additionally, 7.5% of poachers engaged in daily poaching for bushmeat, including species such as Duikers, Rabbits, and Fronted gazelles. Flora species harvested for firewood and charcoal production include *Prosopis africana*, *Parkia oliveri*, *Balanites aegyptica*, and *Acacia senegal*. The study concludes by recommending that regulatory agencies, including the Federal Environmental Protection Commission, the Environmental Impact Assessment Commission, the urban and regional planning agency, and various state environmental protection agencies, develop new strategies for conserving flora and fauna in Nigerian reserves, particularly the Gujba Forest Reserve in Yobe State.

Keywords: Poachers, Civil servant, Communities, Forest guard

Paper type: Research paper

Introduction

Poaching is defined as the illegal hunting or capturing of wild animals, typically associated with violations of land use rights (Oxford Living Dictionary, 2019). The term also encompasses the illegal harvesting of wild plant species (Dietrich and Columbini, 2010). Poaching involves the unlawful killing of wildlife in contravention of established local, federal, or international laws, including any unlicensed taking of animals, hunting out of season, exceeding bag limits, use of prohibited weapons, or trespassing (Lin, 2014). It may further be characterized as any unauthorized killing or capturing of wildlife, particularly species designated as endangered, rare, or protected (Blevins and Edwards, 2009). Poachers target a wide range of wildlife, including birds, reptiles, and large mammals (Wilson-Wade, 2010). Bush meat, wild meat, or game meat refers to meat from non-domesticated mammals, reptiles, amphibians, and birds hunted for food in tropical forests (Nasi *et al.*, 2008). Commercial harvesting and trading of wildlife pose significant threats to biodiversity (Cowlshaw *et al.*, 2005).

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The term bush meat is commonly used for the meat of terrestrial wild mammals hunted for subsistence or commercial purposes throughout the humid tropics of the Americas, Asia, and Africa. In West Africa, particularly Ghana, the Ivory Coast, and Nigeria, the giant African snail is also collected, sold, consumed, and monitored as part of the bush meat trade (Dietrich and Columбини, 2010). To reflect the global scope of wild animal hunting, Resolution 2.64 of the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) General Assembly, adopted in Amman in October 2000, adopted the term wild meat rather than bush meat. The term 'game' is more commonly used for terrestrial wild animals (Hassan *et al.*, 2005). A game reserve, also known as a wildlife preserve or game park (Collins English Dictionary, 2014), is a large area where wild animals live safely or are hunted in a controlled manner for sport (Macmillan, 2017). If hunting is prohibited, a game reserve may be considered a nature reserve; however, a game reserve's primary focus is fauna, whereas a nature reserve is equally concerned with all aspects of native biota, including plants, animals, and fungi.

Many game reserves are located in Africa (Pitman *et al.*, 2016), and most are open to the public, with tourists frequently participating in sightseeing safaris. Historically, the most prominent hunting targets in Africa were the so-called big five game: elephant (*Loxodonta africana*), Cape buffalo (*Syncerus caffer*), and lion (*Panthera pardus*), named for the difficulty and danger involved in hunting them (Crosmary, 2015). Game reserves protect ecosystems and conserve wildlife. Indigenous wildlife in its natural habitat supports population growth at a natural rate. Species threatened by poaching include the African elephant, greater kudu, duiker, reedbuck, bush pig, common warthog, baboon, greater cane rat, black-headed heron (*Ardea melanocephala*), great egret (*Ardea alba*), pied crow (*Corvus albus*), African marsh harrier (*Circus ranivorus*), black kite (*Milvus migrans*), jackal (*Canis aureus*), and rabbit (*Lepus capensis*), all of which are illegally hunted for bush meat (Lindsey and Bento, 2012). In Gujba Forest Reserve, species such as francolin (*Francolinus bicanatus*), black hornbill (*Tockus nasutus*), monitor lizard (*Varanus niloticus*), black monitor (*Varanus exanthematicus*), and squirrel (*Xerus erythropus*) are also illegally hunted for bush meat. Notably, a lion was killed in 2012 by hunters in Gujba after it killed two herders and 30 livestock (Ahmed, 2012). Despite the presence of forest guards and law enforcement agents in Yobe State, biodiversity in these areas continues to decline (Ministry of Environment, 2021).

It is therefore necessary to examine the effects of poaching on selected wild animal species in Gujba Forest Reserve, with the aim of identifying strategies for harmonious coexistence between forest reserve management and local communities. Poaching represents one of the most significant threats to the survival of plant and animal populations, with detrimental effects on biodiversity both within and outside protected areas. As wild animal populations decline, local species are depleted, and ecosystem functionality is disrupted (Lindsey *et al.*, 2012). Fruit-eating vertebrates cannot recover as rapidly as they are removed from forests; as their populations decline, patterns of seed predation and dispersal are altered, leading to the dominance of tree species with large seeds and the local extinction of small-seeded plant species (Redford and Kent, 1992). This study aims to identify wild animal species threatened by poaching and to assess respondents' perceptions of poaching in Gujba Forest Reserve, Yobe State, Nigeria. Wildlife constitutes a valuable component of Nigeria's tourism sector and natural ecology, and must therefore be protected from harm and potential extinction. Efforts should be intensified to minimize poaching and the illegal trade of wild animal species in Nigeria. Several endangered and unique species inhabit the study area, where poaching remains a significant threat. While recent years have seen increased emphasis on reducing international demand for poached products, understanding the persistence of poaching requires examination of local conditions. The research was conducted exclusively in Gujba Forest Reserve, Yobe State, Nigeria, over a period of three months.

Materials and methods

Study Area

Location

Yobe State is situated in the northeastern region of Nigeria and is predominantly agricultural. The state is positioned at approximately longitude 12°00'E and latitude 11°30'N. The research was conducted in the Gujba Forest Reserve, located within the Gujba Local Government Area of Yobe State (Figure 1). Gujba is found at latitude 11°16'08"N and longitude 11°55'49"E. The town of Gujba is situated in the northern part of the forest reserve. The reserve covers a total area of 410 km² (158.3 sq mi), with coordinates ranging from latitude 11°10'N to 11°30'N and longitude 11°50'E to 12°10'E.

Methodology

The research was conducted in the Gujba Forest Reserve, Yobe State, Nigeria, over a period of three months from April 2021 to June 2021

Figure 1: Map Of Nigeria Showing Yobe State
Source: Ministry of Land and Survey

Figure 2: Map of Yobe State Showing Gujba Local Government Area
Source: Ministry of Land and Survey

Figure 3: Map of Gujba Local Government showing Gujba Forest Reserve (Study area)
Source: Ministry of Land and Survey

Data collection

One set of pre-tested questionnaires was used for primary data collection for the study.

The rural appraisal technique was used to source information from the respondents. The questionnaire was administered to the staff of the Ministry of Environment, Poachers, Bush Meat Sellers, and communities around the forest reserve. The questionnaire was categorized into sections A - C. Section A was used to obtain information about the demographic characteristics of the respondent, Section B was used to obtain information about the identification of animal species threatened by poachers in Gujba Forest Reserve, while Section C was used to obtain information about the perception of respondents toward poaching in the study area. To identify animal species threatened by poachers in Gujba Forest Reserve, both a questionnaire and an oral interview were administered to staff from the Ministry of Environment to determine which species are at risk. Some Forest guards, poachers, and bush meat sellers from Gujba, particularly those living near the forest reserve, were also contacted for relevant information.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The Krejcie and Morgan (1970) method of determining the sample size was used. The questionnaire was based on population size: the larger the population, the more copies were allocated to the area (Table 1). Due to the lack of reliable population data, the number of copies of the questionnaire allocated to each town/village was determined based on the projected 2021 population percentages. The National Population recommends using population projections because Nigeria's census data is inadequate.

$$Pt. = Po (1+r)^n$$

Where:

Pt. = population of the year i.e. 2021

Po = Previous Population i.e. 2006

r= Growth rate i.e. 3%

n= Interval between Pt. and Po i.e. 15 years

Purposive sampling was used in the study. Seven villages/towns were selected, namely, Gujba, Buni Yadi, Wagir, Katarko, Goniri, Buni Gari, and Damaturu. 200 copies of the questionnaire were administered. Fifty-two 52 (26%) questionnaires at Buni Yadi, Goniri 23 (11%), Katarko 9 (4%), Wagir 9 (5%), Gujba 8 (4%), Buni Gari 6 (3%), and Damaturu 93 (47%). Table 1. According to the National Population Commission, Yobe State has a population of 2,321,339, with a growth rate of 3% and a projected population of 3,616,570 as of 2021. The study local government area has a population of 130,088 (2006 census) and is projected to be 202,664 as of 2021.

Table 1 Sample size of the study area

Study area	Population 2006	Projected population 2021	Sample size	Percentage %
Buni yadi	26,755	41,682	52	26%
Goniri	11,673	18,185	23	11%
Damaturu	48,014	74,801	93	47%
Katarko	4,008	6,244	9	4%
Wagir	4,586	7,145	9	5%
Gujba	3,902	6,079	8	4%
Buni gari	3,269	5,093	6	3%
Total	102,207	159,229	200	100%

Source : Field Survey

Data Analysis

All results presented in Table 2 were analyzed using the Pearson chi-square test. The analysis indicates that the calculated value of the Pearson chi-square test exceeds the critical tabulated value at $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the observed frequency differs significantly from the expected frequency. This difference is substantial enough to be considered statistically significant, as shown in Appendix I.

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$$

Where: O = Observed scores
 E = Expected scores
 Σ = Summation sign (Adesoye 2004)

Table 2: Socio economic Characteristic of the Respondents

Demographic characteristic	frequency	percentage (%)
Age class		
10-20	12	6
21-30	54	27
31-40	68	34
41-50	43	21.5
>50	23	11.5
Total	200	100
Gender		
Male	200	100
Female	0	0
Total	200	100
Marital status		
Married	150	75
Single	50	25
Total	200	100
Educational background		
None	0	0
Arabic	71	35
Primary	11	5.5
Secondary	66	33
Tertiary	52	26
Total	200	100
Number of household size		
2-3	37	18.5
4-6	58	29
7-8	28	14
>8	34	17
Single	43	21.5
Total	200	100
Occupation		
Farmer	48	24
Civil servant	56	28
Poacher	50	25
Forest guard	10	5
Bush meat seller	18	9
Firewood seller	18	9
Total	200	100
Income per week		
1000-5000	21	10.5
6000-10,000	30	15

Figure 2: Social Economic Characteristic

11000-15000	25	12.5
≥ 15000	19	9.5
Others	105	52.5
Total	200	100

Source: Field Survey 2021

Results

Wild Animal Species Threatened by Poaching

According to Table 3, 69.5% of respondents indicated that wild animal species are killed by poachers in the Gujba forest reserve for bush meat, as illustrated in table 3. The skins of python and spotted hyena, shown in Plates 1 and 2, as well as the heads of certain wild animals and various plant stems and leaves, are reportedly used for traditional medicine. In March 2021, a Patas monkey was killed, followed by the poaching of an African hyena and a python in April 2021. Plates 1 and 2 further depict the skins of the hyena and python, along with other animal parts used for medicinal purposes. Additional species, including rabbit, mongoose, francolin, black monitor, and monitor lizard, were also reported killed outside the study area. Conversely, 30.5% of respondents disagreed, stating they did not observe the animals killed by poachers after such incidents.

Table 3: Marital Status towards Age Group

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	146.419 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	168.169	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	110.784	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	200		

Table 4: Educational background towards Age Group

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	268.155 ^a	8	.000
Likelihood Ratio	304.194	8	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	155.469	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	200		

Table 5: Household Size toward age group

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	339.208 ^a	16	.000
Likelihood Ratio	358.091	16	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	163.533	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	200		

Table 6: Occupation toward Age Group

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	396.199 ^a	20	.000
Likelihood Ratio	374.445	20	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	163.513	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	200		

Table 7: Socio Economic Status towards Age group

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	308.982 ^a	16	.000
Likelihood Ratio	301.119	16	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	137.937	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	200		

Table 8: Name of some Species of wild animals threatened in Gujba forest reserve by Poachers for Bush Meat

English name	Scientific name	Hausa name
Jackal	<i>Caris auroe</i>	Dila
Spotted hyena	<i>Crocota - crocuta</i>	Kura
Red fronted gazelle	<i>Gazelle rufifrons</i>	Barewa
Porcupines	<i>Hystrix cristata</i>	Baguwa
Rabbit	<i>Lepus capensis</i>	Zomo
Mongoose	<i>Mongus mungo</i>	Dage
Warthog	<i>Phacochoerus africana</i>	Mugun dawa
Lungfish	<i>Protopterus annectues</i>	Gaiwa
Python	<i>Python sabae</i>	Mesa
Duiker	<i>Syfvicapra grimmia</i>	Gada
Francolin	<i>Francolinus bicalcaratus</i>	Fakara
Black horn bill	<i>Tuckucs nasutus</i>	Zabuwa
Monitor lizard	<i>Veranus niloticus</i>	Guza
Monitor black	<i>Verus exanthematicus</i>	Damo
Squirrel	<i>Xerus erythropus</i>	Kurege

Source: Field Survey 2021

Plate 1: Poachers display fresh skin of python
Source: Field Survey 2021

Plate 2: Poacher display Skin of Spotted Hyena
Source: Field Survey 2021

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Plate 3: Bush Meat killed by Poachers from Gujba Forest Reserve

Table 9: Poached animals sold in the study area.

English name	Scientific name	Hausa name
Rabbit	<i>Lepus capensis</i>	Zomo
Lungfish	<i>Protopterus annectues</i>	Gaiwa
Red fronted gazelle	<i>Gazelle rufifrons</i>	Barewa
Duiker	<i>Syfvicapra grimmia</i>	Gada
Francolin	<i>Francolinus bicalcanatus</i>	Fakara
Black horn bill	<i>Tuckucs nasutus</i>	Zabuwa
Monitor lizard	<i>Veranus niloticus</i>	Guza
Monitor black	<i>Verus exanthematicus</i>	Damo
Squirrel	<i>Xerus erythropus</i>	Kurege

Source: Field Survey 2021

Respondent Perceptions of Poaching in the Gujba Forest Reserve

Poaching has a significant negative impact on the majority of the community, primarily due to deforestation, as illustrated in Plate 12. Many economic tree species that serve as sources of income for local communities are harvested for firewood, charcoal, and traditional medicine. According to Figure 9, 82.5% of respondents reported that trees are destroyed within the Gujba Forest Reserve for firewood and charcoal production, while 17.5% indicated a lack of knowledge regarding poaching. Additionally, 80.5% of respondents agreed that government intervention is necessary, specifically through the provision of alternative income sources and energy options such as kerosene or electricity, to mitigate poaching activities. Respondents further suggested that employing poachers and community members, particularly local leaders, to manage the reserve, followed by the enforcement of laws to protect wildlife, would help secure economic tree species. Legal measures should prohibit poaching at all times within the reserve. Tree species affected by deforestation in the study area include Kuka (*Adonsonia digitata*), Dakwara (*Acacia senegal*), Marke (*Anogeisus leiocarpus*), Aduwa (*Balanite aegyptiaca*), Taura (*Detarium senegalensis*), Tamiya (*Tamarindus indica*), Dorawa (*Pakia oliveri*), Kirya (*Prosopis africana*), Madubiya (*Pterocarpus erinaceus*), and Madachi (*Khaya senegalensis*).

Discussion

Species of Wild Animals Threatened by Poaching

Findings presented in Table 3 indicate that several animal species in the study area are threatened by poaching. A total of 69.5% of respondents agreed that wild animal species are threatened and killed for bushmeat, as illustrated in table 4. Additionally, animal skins and other body parts are used for traditional medicine, as shown in table 1 and 3.

These results are consistent with the findings of Lindsey and Bento (2012), who reported that African elephants (*Loxodonta africana*), lions (*Panthera leo*), greater kudu (*Tragelaphus strepsiceros*), elands (*Taurotragus oryx*), impala (*Aepyceros melampus*), red forest duiker (*Cephalophus natalensis*), reedbuck (*Redunca arundinum*), Cape bushbuck (*Tragelaphus sylvaticus*), bush pig (*Potamochoerus larvatus*), common warthog (*Phacochoerus africanus*), baboon (*Papio ursinus*), and greater cane rat (*Thryonomys swinderianus*) are illegally hunted for the bushmeat trade in Mozambique. Table 3 also identifies species that are poached and sold alive, while Table 5 lists species that have become rare due to poaching in the study area. Regarding the impact of poaching, 77.5% of respondents agreed that poaching reduces the availability of animals, with species such as hyena, elephant, leopard, and baboon now considered rare in the study area. This finding aligns with Milliken and Shaw (2012), who noted that wild animal species threatened by poaching in Africa include the Amur leopard, African elephant, Amur tiger, black rhinoceros, Bengal tiger, hawksbill turtle, green turtle, Javan rhinoceros, leatherback turtle, orangutan, Malayan tiger, Sumatran tiger, Sumatran rhinoceros, and white rhinoceros.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The study identified poaching as a significant threat to the survival of wild animals in the study area. Poaching contributes to declines in wildlife populations, species extinction, habitat loss, and economic losses. Wild animals are killed for bushmeat, and their skins and other body parts are used for traditional medicine. Additionally, poachers and some local communities cut trees for firewood and charcoal production.

Recommendations

1. It is recommended that the government actively involve poachers and local communities, particularly their leaders, in the management of the forest reserve to enhance effectiveness in curbing large-scale poaching and deforestation.
2. Several factors undermine conservation effectiveness in Nigeria, particularly in the Gujba Forest Reserve. Notably, inadequate and irregular electricity supply compels citizens, especially in rural communities, to cut trees for firewood used in cooking and other domestic activities, which accelerates soil erosion and wildlife loss. The government should therefore provide alternative energy sources, such as kerosene and cooking gas, to reduce dependence on firewood.
3. Regulatory agencies, including the Federal Environmental Protection Commission, the Environmental Impact Assessment Commission, the Urban and Regional Planning Agency, and state environmental protection agencies, should develop and implement new strategies to conserve wild animals in Nigerian reserves, with particular emphasis on the Gujba Forest Reserve in Yobe State.
4. The government should implement necessary measures to manage the Gujba Forest Reserve effectively, ensuring the preservation of remaining plant and animal species and preventing their extinction.

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Appendix

Plate 4: Poacher with live Monitor Lizard
Source: Field Survey 2021

Plate 6: Poacher with his live Patas Monkey
Source: Field Survey 2021

Plate 7: Factory for chorcoal production in the study area.